

Isolation of pentonic acid-3-deoxy-4-lactone and peganine-N-oxide from *Adhatoda vasica*

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Present paper deals with the isolation of two compounds namely pentonic acid-3-deoxy-4-lactone and peganine-N-oxide alongwith vasicine from the methanol extract of aerial parts of *Adhatoda vasica*. Pentonic acid-3-deoxy-4-lactone has been isolated for the first time from nature and peganine-N-oxide is reported first time from this plant. The structures of compounds were elucidated by spectroscopic methods.

Keywords: *Adhatoda vasica*, *Justica adhtoda*, Adosa, pentonic acid-3-deoxy-4-lactone, peganine-N-oxide.

Introduction

Adhatoda vasica or *Justica adhtoda*, is commonly known as 'Vasaka' or 'Adosa'. It is a small, evergreen shrub growing many regions of India. It is widely used for the treatment of cough, asthma, phlegm, bleeding hemorrhoids, for both adults and youth¹.

Results and discussion

Chromatographic separation of the methanol extract of dried and powdered aerial part of *Adhatoda vasica* yielded pentonic acid-3-deoxy-4-lactone, aziridine-type base peganine-N-oxide along with vasicine. Pentonic acid-3-deoxy-4-lactone and peganine-N-oxide have been isolated first time from this plant. Earlier peganine-N-oxide (**3**) was isolated from epigeal part of *Nitraria komarovii*². All the compounds were identified with the help of modern spectroscopic techniques.

Fig. 1. Structures of compounds 1-3.

Experimental

The NMR spectra were recorded in CD₃OD on JEOL AL-300 MHz FTNMR instrument. Mass spectra (ESI MS) were

recorded on Water Xevo G2S Q-TOF spectrometer using MeOH solvent. IR spectra were obtained by Bruker FT-IR spectrophotometer. Melting points were uncorrected.

Extraction and isolation:

The aerial parts of *Adhatoda vasica* was air-dried for 14 days and then crushed to obtain plant material (2 kg). Then above material was soaked in MeOH for 2 days. After that filtrate was concentrated using rotary evaporator at 45°C *in vacuo* to obtain 90 g crude extract. The crude extract was dissolved in distilled H₂O and first extracted with hexane and then with EtOAc. Then ethylacetate extract (50 g) was loaded on silica gel eluted with hexane-ethylacetate mixtures. Many fractions were collected, from which alike fractions were mixed. This fraction was again chromatographed on silica gel, using CHCl₃ and MeOH as eluent. Fraction eluted with CHCl₃-MeOH (90:10) was purified by preparative TLC to afforded pentonic acid-3-deoxy-4-lactone (**1**), vasicine (**2**) and peganine-N-oxide (**3**).

Pentonic acid-3-deoxy-4-lactone (1): 20 mg, colourless oil, *m/z* 132.11; HR-ESI-MS *m/z* 133.0518 [M+H]⁺ (calcd. for C₅H₉O₄ 133.04); IR ν_{\max} (KBr): 3500 (OH), 2800 (CH₂), 1740, 1200 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CD₃OD): δ 2.32 (1H, H-4, dd, *J* 18, 2.6 Hz), 2.89 (1H, H-4, dd, *J* 18, 6.9 Hz), 3.65–3.78 (2H, H-6, m), 4.35 (1H, dd, H-5, *J* 6.9, 3.3 Hz), 4.43 (1H, H-3, m); ¹³C NMR (CD₃OD, 75.45 MHz): δ 39.16 (CH₂-), 62.51, 69.70, 90.19, 178.68 (C=O). Further it was identified as 3-hydroxy-5-(hydroxymethyl)-dihydro-furan-2(3*H*)-one or pentonic acid-3-deoxy- γ -lactone.

Vasicine (2): 20 mg, white crystals, m.p. 212–213°C (Lit.^{3,4} 213–214°C); HR-ESI-MS m/z 189.038 [M+H]⁺ (calcd. for C₁₁H₁₃N₂O 189.05); UV (EtOH) λ_{\max} 213, 218, 289 nm; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CD₃OD): δ 1.98 (1H, m, H-2), 2.42 (1H, m, H-2), 3.30 (1H, m, H-1), 3.45 (1H, m, H-1), 4.67 (3H, m, H-9, 3), 6.96–7.04 (3H, m, H-6, 7, 8), 7.17 (1H, m, H-5); ¹³C NMR (CD₃OD, 75.45 MHz): δ 30.54, 47.70, 50.02, 72.41, 120.39, 123.38, 126.02, 127.38, 129.48, 141.73, 164.50.

Peganine-N-oxide (3): 15 mg, white crystals, m.p. 205–207°C (Lit.² 207–208°C); MS m/z 204 (M)⁺ C₁₁H₁₂N₂O₂; IR (KBr): 770 (*o*-disubstituted benzene ring), 1230, 1265, 1464, 1511, 1586, 1631 (C-C, C-N), 2862, 2942, 3150 (OH) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CD₃OD): δ 2.12 (1H, m), 2.62 (1H, m), 3.60–3.70 (2H, m), 4.74 (2H, t), 5.04 (1H, m), 7.09–7.29 (4H, m, H-5,6,7,8); ¹³C NMR (CD₃OD, 75.45 MHz): δ 30.17 (CH₂-), 47.53, 51.55, 72.50, 118.58, 119.16, 127.97, 128.12, 130.31, 133.85, 164.73.

Conclusions

We have isolated pentonic acid-3-deoxy-4-lactone and peganine-N-oxide from the methanolic extract of aerial parts of *A. vasica*. It is first report of isolation of these compounds from this plant.

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Supporting Information

Files are attached.

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